

Supplementary material

**Pan-genome of the genus *Streptomyces*
and prioritization of biosynthetic gene
clusters with potential to produce antibiotic
compounds**

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Supplementary Figure S1. Genome quality evaluation through Benchmarking Universal Single-copy Orthologs (BUSCOs).

Supplementary Figure S2. Three-dimensional plot of genome size, number of proteins and percentage G+C of the 121 *Streptomyces* strains analyzed.

Supplementary Figure S3. Distribution of Jaccard distance for the genomes of 121 *Streptomyces* when presence or absence of a gene family in a genome is determined by **(A)** Roary and **(B)** Micropan. The Jaccard distance was evaluated using an approach of comparing all-against-all genomes. For two set of gene clusters belonging to a genome A and B, respectively, the Jaccard distance is defined as follow: $J(A, B) = 1 - \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|}$

Tree scale: 0.1

Supplementary Figure S4. Distribution of Biosynthetic Gene Clusters (BGCs) in the 121 *Streptomyces* strains analyzed. *Streptomyces* strains are organized by the core-genome phylogenetic tree and highlighted according to their isolation source. *Streptomyces* strains are segmented in 3 main clades. In red: clade1, yellow: clade 2 and blue: clade 3.

Supplementary Figure S5. Multiple genome alignment performed with the progressiveMauve algorithm for *S. coelicolor* A3(2), *S. lividans* TK24 and *Streptomyces* sp. CB0900.

S. autolyticus CGMCC0516
S. malaysiensis DSM 4137
S. sp. M56
S. violaceus Tu 4113
S. hygrosopicus XM201
S. sp. 11-1-2
S. koyangensis VK460T
S. albidoflavus J1074
S. albidoflavus SM254
S. sp. SM17
S. sampsonii KJ40
S. sp. FR-008
S. fulvissimus DSM 40593
S. sp. S8
S. sp. CFMR 7
S. bacillaris ATCC 15855
S. sp. DUT11
S. violaceus NRRL 521
S. griseus NBRC 13350
S. sp. S063
S. sp. Tue6075
S. globisporus C-1027
S. globisporus TFH56
S. clavuligerus ATCC 27064
S. clavuligerus F1265
S. clavuligerus F613-1
S. hygrosopicus kimoneus KCTC 1717
S. hygrosopicus jinggangensis 5008
S. hygrosopicus jinggangensis TL01
S. ambofaciens ATCC 23877
S. ambofaciens DSM 40697
S. sp. KP82
S. sp. CB09001
S. coelicolor A3(2)
S. lividans TK24
S. alvaresus KLBMP 5084
S. parvulus 2297
S. pactum ACT 12
S. sp. S552
S. lincolniensis LC-G
S. lincolniensis NRRL 2936
S. cyanosporus nonyanogenus NMHT 1
S. keulenhoekii DSM 42122
S. pluripotens MUSC 137
S. seoulensis KCTC 9819
S. sp. endophyte N2
S. sp. 2022
S. purisicabiei TW151
S. collinus Tu 365
S. griseochromogenes ATCC 14511
S. nigra 452
S. sp. MW45
S. sp. CTFB01
S. sp. GGCP4
S. griseorubiginosus 3E-1
S. sp. CC0208
S. sp. ZFG47
S. actinosus ATCC 25421
S. albus KCS-25
S. qaidamensis S10
S. sp. Go-475
S. fungicidus TX03120
S. sp. WAC 01438
S. griseoviridis F1-27
S. sp. SAT1
S. avermilis MA-4680
S. dengpaensis XZH999
S. scabiei 87.22
S. sp. P3
S. albus ZD111
S. albus KCS-25
S. albus DSM 41398
S. sp. 769
S. albus CK-15
S. albus NK660
S. lydicus 103
S. lydicus G593/23
S. sp. MOE7
S. lydicus WYEC 108
S. sp. NEAL-57G52
S. gilvosporeus F607
S. lydicus AD2
S. globosus soil
S. lavenderulae lavenderulae CCM 3239
S. sp. Mq1
S. sp. 3211
S. sp. S9e12
S. sp. TN59
S. sp. 101-wmd
S. albobolus MDJK44
S. alfalae ACCC40021
S. fradiae NK2-259
S. formicae KY
S. sp. WAC 01529
S. bingchengensis BCW-1
S. xinghaiensis S187
S. luteovorticillatus CGMCC 15060
S. albrechtii MDJK11
S. divoreticus divoreticus ATCC 31159
S. albus SCSO 3406
S. pratensis ATCC 33331
S. sp. PAMC26508
S. sp. SM18
S. sp. Sv. ACTE SirexAA-E
S. spongiosa HM0071
S. spongiosa HM0071
S. tirandamyricinus HM0039
S. lunaeolactis MM109
S. pristinaespiralis HCCB 10218
S. niveus SCSO 3406
S. sp. G550A-7
S. naitolavendulae H95426
S. orollans A10131
S. sp. WAC0288
S. venezuelae NRRL B-65442
S. vietnamensis GPMV4-0001
S. sp. CLZ509
S. sp. WAC 06738
S. sp. CNQ-509
S. sp. WAC 06738
S. cattedya NRRL 8057
S. xiamenensis 318
S. sp. CNQ-509
S. sp. WAC 06738

Isolation source
 soil
 rhizosphere
 marine
 insect-associated
 mammal-associated
 plant-associated
 fungus-associated
 engineered
 lichen-associated
 missing

Supplementary Figure S6. Heat map representing the average nucleotide identity (ANI) values of the compared strains. The colors above the heat map represent the isolation source of the organisms. The dendrogram was generated with the UPGMA method available in the library Seaborn of Python.

Supplementary Figure S7. Secondary structure of a putative non-coding RNA detected by RNAz and located in an intergenic region (IGR) highly conserved in the clade 1 of the *Streptomyces* core genome phylogenetic tree. The consensus minimum free energy (MFE) structure was depicted with RNAfold. The color bar indicates the base-pair probabilities. The flanking genes of the IGR are indicated by arrows. If one of the flanking genes potentially interacts with part of the sequence of the IGR, the arrow is depicted in orange. The region of interaction with the best hit predicted by IntaRNA 2.0 is showed in the bottom of the figure. The representative strain used to detect the possible targets of this IGR was *Streptomyces albulus* NK660.

Supplementary Figure S8. Secondary structure of a putative non-coding RNA detected by RNAz and located in an intergenic region (IGR) highly conserved in the clade 1 of the *Streptomyces* core genome phylogenetic tree. The consensus minimum free energy (MFE) structure was depicted with RNAfold. The color bar indicates the base-pair probabilities. The flanking genes of the IGR are indicated by arrows. If one of the flanking genes potentially interacts with part of the sequence of the IGR, the arrow is depicted in orange. The region of interaction with the best hit predicted by IntaRNA 2.0 is showed in the bottom of the figure. The representative strain used to detect the possible targets of this IGR was *Streptomyces violaceusniger* Tu 4113.

Target (top) : SMD11_RS15435
 Query (bottom) : Cluster_25022_GCF_002192455.1_ASM219245v1_genomic.gbff_SMD11_RS21825.p01_SMD11_RS21830.p01_CO_F

84		150
5'-CUG..ACGAC	GCUACC C G CC G CC CAGGUG GA	
CCC CGCCGACG	GUGCC UCUUCU CGA UGC CU GAC ACC UGCCUUCUC	
GGG GUGGCUGC	CACGG AGAAGA GCU ACG GA CUG UGG AUGGARGGGG	
3'-CAGUA A AA	A CC G A GG	GUAAA..AGG-5'
208		153

Supplementary Figure S10. Secondary structure of a putative non-coding RNA detected by RNAz and located in an intergenic region (IGR) highly conserved in the clade 1 of the *Streptomyces* core genome phylogenetic tree. The consensus minimum free energy (MFE) structure was depicted with RNAfold. The color bar indicates the base-pair probabilities. The flanking genes of the IGR are indicated by arrows. If one of the flanking genes potentially interacts with part of the sequence of the IGR, the arrow is depicted in orange. The region of interaction with the best hit predicted by IntaRNA 2.0 is showed in the bottom of the figure. The representative strain used to detect the possible targets of this IGR was *Streptomyces albireticuli* MDJK11.

Supplementary Figure S11. Secondary structure of a putative non-coding RNA detected by RNAz and located in an intergenic region (IGR) highly conserved in the clade 1 of the *Streptomyces* core genome phylogenetic tree. The consensus minimum free energy (MFE) structure was depicted with RNAfold. The color bar indicates the base-pair probabilities. The flanking genes of the IGR are indicated by arrows. If one of the flanking genes potentially interacts with part of the sequence of the IGR, the arrow is depicted in orange. The region of interaction with the best hit predicted by IntaRNA 2.0 is showed in the bottom of the figure. The representative strain used to detect the possible targets of this IGR was *Streptomyces bingchengensis* BCW-1.

Supplementary Figure S12. Secondary structure of a putative non-coding RNA detected by RNAz and located in an intergenic region (IGR) highly conserved in the clade 1 of the *Streptomyces* core genome phylogenetic tree. The consensus minimum free energy (MFE) structure was depicted with RNAfold. The color bar indicates the base-pair probabilities. The flanking genes of the IGR are indicated by arrows. If one of the flanking genes potentially interacts with part of the sequence of the IGR, the arrow is depicted in orange. The region of interaction with the best hit predicted by IntaRNA 2.0 is showed in the bottom of the figure. The representative strain used to detect the possible targets of this IGR was *Streptomyces bingchengensis* BCW-1.

Supplementary Figure S13. Secondary structure of a putative non-coding RNA detected by RNAz and located in an intergenic region (IGR) highly conserved in the clade 1 of the *Streptomyces* core genome phylogenetic tree. The consensus minimum free energy (MFE) structure was depicted with RNAfold. The color bar indicates the base-pair probabilities. The flanking genes of the IGR are indicated by arrows. If one of the flanking genes potentially interacts with part of the sequence of the IGR, the arrow is depicted in orange. The region of interaction with the best hit predicted by IntaRNA 2.0 is showed in the bottom of the figure. The representative strain used to detect the possible targets of this IGR was *Streptomyces gilvosporeus* F607.

Supplementary Figure S14. Secondary structure of a putative non-coding RNA detected by RNAz and located in an intergenic region (IGR) highly conserved in the clade 1 of the *Streptomyces* core genome phylogenetic tree. The consensus minimum free energy (MFE) structure was depicted with RNAfold. The color bar indicates the base-pair probabilities. The flanking genes of the IGR are indicated by arrows. If one of the flanking genes potentially interacts with part of the sequence of the IGR, the arrow is depicted in orange. The region of interaction with the best hit predicted by IntaRNA 2.0 is showed in the bottom of the figure. The representative strain used to detect the possible targets of this IGR was *Streptomyces gilvosporeus* F607.

Supplementary Figure S15. Secondary structure of a putative non-coding RNA detected by RNAz and located in an intergenic region (IGR) highly conserved in the clade 1 of the *Streptomyces* core genome phylogenetic tree. The consensus minimum free energy (MFE) structure was depicted with RNAfold. The color bar indicates the base-pair probabilities. The flanking genes of the IGR are indicated by arrows. If one of the flanking genes potentially interacts with part of the sequence of the IGR, the arrow is depicted in orange. The region of interaction with the best hit predicted by IntaRNA 2.0 is showed in the bottom of the figure. The representative strain used to detect the possible targets of this IGR was *Streptomyces lydicus* A02.

Supplementary Figure S16. Secondary structure of a putative non-coding RNA detected by RNAz and located in an intergenic region (IGR) highly conserved in the clade 1 of the *Streptomyces* core genome phylogenetic tree. The consensus minimum free energy (MFE) structure was depicted with RNAfold. The color bar indicates the base-pair probabilities. The flanking genes of the IGR are indicated by arrows. If one of the flanking genes potentially interacts with part of the sequence of the IGR, the arrow is depicted in orange. The region of interaction with the best hit predicted by IntaRNA 2.0 is showed in the bottom of the figure. The representative strain used to detect the possible targets of this IGR was *Streptomyces olivoreticuli olivoreticuli* ATCC 31159.

Target (top) : DDQ41_RS24645
 Query (bottom) : Cluster_12890_GCF_003122365.1_ASM312236v1_genomic.gbff_DDQ41_RS24655.p01_DDQ41_RS24660.p01_CO_F

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      57                                     112
      |                                     |
5'-UGA..AGCCA   C   A   ACCGAUCCCC   CCGC   C   UCCCC..GCG-3'
      CGCAC   CGGG GCCACUCCGUG   UGC   CCCG UC   UCCGACCCCC
      |||||   |||| | ||||| |||||   |||   |||| | |   ||||| |||||
      GCGUG   GCCC CGGUGGGGCAC   AUG   GGGC AG   AGGCUGGGGG
3'-CAG..UUACA   AAGU   A   AA   UA   CCUUU..CGC-5'
      234                                     187
  
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Supplementary Figure S17. Secondary structure of a putative non-coding RNA detected by RNAz and located in an intergenic region (IGR) highly conserved in the clade 2 of the *Streptomyces* core genome phylogenetic tree. The consensus minimum free energy (MFE) structure was depicted with RNAfold. The color bar indicates the base-pair probabilities. The flanking genes of the IGR are indicated by arrows. If one of the flanking genes potentially interacts with part of the sequence of the IGR, the arrow is depicted in orange. The region of interaction with the best hit predicted by IntaRNA 2.0 is showed in the bottom of the figure. The representative strain used to detect the possible targets of this IGR was *Streptomyces spongiicola* HNM0071.

Supplementary Figure S18. Secondary structure of a putative non-coding RNA detected by RNaz and located in an intergenic region (IGR) highly conserved in the clade 3 of the *Streptomyces* core genome phylogenetic tree. The consensus minimum free energy (MFE) structure was depicted with RNAfold. The color bar indicates the base-pair probabilities. The flanking genes of the IGR are indicated by arrows. If one of the flanking genes potentially interacts with part of the sequence of the IGR, the arrow is depicted in orange. The region of interaction with the best hit predicted by IntaRNA 2.0 is showed in the bottom of the figure. The representative strain used to detect the possible targets of this IGR was *Streptomyces scabiei* 87.22.

Target (top) : CNQ36_RS14660
 Query (bottom) : Cluster_73940_GCF_003665435.1_ASM366543v1_genomic.gbff_CNQ36_RS28655.p01_CNQ36_RS28660.p01_CO_F

11		50
5'-GGACUGAAUC	AA ACUAU	C AGUGA..GCC-3'
CCGGG UGCGUC	GGACCGUCGUAG	ACUCAUCG
GGCC ACGCAG	CCUGGCAGCGAUC	UGAGUAGC
3'-AAG..CUCCA	A G	AAGUACCGCA GCAUG..ACG-5'
168		124

Supplementary Figure S19. Secondary structure of a putative non-coding RNA detected by RNAz and located in an intergenic region (IGR) highly conserved in the clade 3 of the *Streptomyces* core genome phylogenetic tree. The consensus minimum free energy (MFE) structure was depicted with RNAfold. The color bar indicates the base-pair probabilities. The flanking genes of the IGR are indicated by arrows. If one of the flanking genes potentially interacts with part of the sequence of the IGR, the arrow is depicted in orange. The region of interaction with the best hit predicted by IntaRNA 2.0 is showed in the bottom of the figure. The representative strain used to detect the possible targets of this IGR was *Streptomyces fungicidicus* TXX3120.

Supplementary Figure S20. Secondary structure of a putative non-coding RNA detected by RNAz and located in an intergenic region (IGR) highly conserved in the clade 3 of the *Streptomyces* core genome phylogenetic tree. The consensus minimum free energy (MFE) structure was depicted with RNAfold. The color bar indicates the base-pair probabilities. The flanking genes of the IGR are indicated by arrows. If one of the flanking genes potentially interacts with part of the sequence of the IGR, the arrow is depicted in orange. The region of interaction with the best hit predicted by IntaRNA 2.0 is showed in the bottom of the figure. The representative strain used to detect the possible targets of this IGR was *Streptomyces* sp. P3.

Supplementary Figure S21. Functional description of the categories of the pan-genome for (A) Roary and (B) Micropan by annotations of Gene Ontology (GO). Only the categories with significant differences (p -value < 0.01) in each pan-genome category after a Pearson's chi-squared test of homogeneity were depicted in the plot. "Core" label includes both core and soft-core genome.

Supplementary Figure S22. Multiple genome alignment performed with the progressiveMauve algorithm for *S. hygroscopicus* XM201, *Streptomyces* sp. 11-1-2 and *S. violaceusniger* Tu 4113.

Supplementary Figure S23. Multiple genome alignment performed with the progressiveMauve algorithm for *S. lydicus* WYEC 108 and *Streptomyces* sp. NEAU-S7GS2.

Supplementary Figure S24. Multiple genome alignment performed with the progressiveMauve algorithm for *S. lydicus* A02 and *S. gilvosporeus* F607.

Supplementary Figure S25. Multiple genome alignment performed with the progressiveMauve algorithm for *S. lydicus* 103, *S. lydicus* GS93 23 and *Streptomyces* sp. MOE7.

Supplementary Figure S26. Multiple genome alignment performed with the progressiveMauve algorithm for *S. autolyticus* CGMCC0516, *S. malaysiensis* DSM 4137 and *Streptomyces* sp. M56.

Supplementary Figure S27. Multiple genome alignment performed with the progressiveMauve algorithm for *S. pratensis* ATCC 33331 and *Streptomyces* sp. PAMC26508.

Supplementary Figure S28. Multiple genome alignment performed with the progressiveMauve algorithm for *S. bacillaris* ATCC 15855, *Streptomyces* sp. DUT11, *Streptomyces* sp. CFMR7 and *Streptomyces* sp. S8.

Supplementary Figure S29. Multiple genome alignment performed with the progressiveMauve algorithm for *S. globisporus* C-1027, *S. globisporus* TFH56, *Streptomyces* sp. 6063 and *Streptomyces* sp. Tue6075.

Supplementary Figure S30. Multiple genome alignment performed with the progressiveMauve algorithm for *S. fradiae* NKZ-259 and *S. alfaiae* ACCC40021.

Supplementary Figure S31. Multiple genome alignment performed with the progressiveMauve algorithm for *S. koyangensis* VK-A60T, *S. sampsonii* KJ40, and *Streptomyces* sp. Fr-008, *S. albidiflavus* J1074, *S. albidiflavus* SM254 and *Streptomyces* sp. SM17.